
Impact, Challenges, and Support System of Internet Use in Universities of Kalyana Karnataka: A Study of Students and Research Scholars

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Abstract

This study investigates patterns of internet use and levels of digital literacy among students and research scholars at universities in the Kalyana Karnataka region. The data were collected using a structured questionnaire from a sample of 483 respondents, comprising of 354 PG students and 129 research scholars in 5 Universities of the said region. The study highlighted that both students and research scholars widely use the internet for academic and research activities, with the majority of them access it daily and stated its impact as highly positive on academic performance and research productivity. The findings also revealed that lack of skills and inadequate technical support from universities hinder the effective use. Other challenges are power cuts and internet addiction, which are reported at a lower level by respondents. Overall, the study reveals that use of internet plays an important role in enhancing teaching, learning, and research activities in the universities of Kalyana Karnataka region

Keywords

Internet, Impact of Internet Resources, Kalyana Karnataka, Challenges

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1. Introduction

The rapid development of internet technologies has fundamentally transformed higher education worldwide, creating new opportunities for learning, research, and knowledge dissemination (Alenezi et al., 2023). In higher educational institutions of India, the integration of internet resources has become increasingly significant for students and research scholars (Sethi et al., 2023). However, the acceptance and effective utilisation of internet-based technologies propose a multifaceted landscape characterised by significant regional differences, infrastructural challenges, and institutional support issues (Aashish & Rohit, 2024).

In India, there are over 1,000 universities and 40,000 colleges that persist, serving millions of students across vastly different geographic, economic, and cultural contexts. In this set-up the internet technology has been unevenly distributed indicating a broader level of digital inequality. Higher educational institutions in urban areas often have access to high-speed Internet connectivity and advanced ICT infrastructure, whereas rural colleges and universities continue to struggle for basic Internet access (Dogra, 2025).

The Internet has its impact on learning and research outcomes in higher educational institutions. The use of internet has been accelerated in recent years due to the comfort it provides in learning and teaching in universities (Dhotre & Banubakode, 2021). Internet tools are highly influencing the academic and research activities (Malik et al., 2024). Hence, understanding the multifaceted nature of internet use among students and research scholars in Universities is essential to know its impact on their academic and research activities. Simultaneously, the challenges before effective use of the Internet can also be identified. The study intends to find out the impact and challenges of using Internet among the students and research scholars of 5 selected Universities of Kalyana Karnataka region in Karnataka state. The study also aims to find out the support from the Universities to provide the standardized internet tools to support academic and research activities.

2. Review of Literature

The extent of internet use among students and research scholars has been widely studied and reports in universities and educational institutions. Several studies show that most users access the internet daily for academic and research purposes. A study by

Singh and Pant in 2013 found that 92.30% of research scholars used the internet regularly to access e-journals, download articles, and communicate. Likewise, Adekunmisi et al. (2013) reported that 32.5% of students used the internet daily and 37.5% weekly, showing dependable use of Internet. Other study witnessed that 86.19% of respondents were aware of and actively used internet tools and services for academic works. This indicates that internet use has become a norm among the users and essential part of academic and research life.

Previous studies have constantly highlighted the rising influence of internet use on academic activities, digital behaviour, and learning methods among students in higher education. Adekunmisi et al. (2013) found that students frequently used the internet for assignments, research, preparation for examination, and communication with faculty members, which supported academic accomplishment and knowledge growth positively. Similarly, Ogedebe et al. (2012) reported that internet access enhanced students' ability to do research and access relevant scholarly information. Studies by Sampath Kumar and Manjunath (2013) and Chakraborty et al. (2020) further highlighted that internet is mainly used for academic purposes that improves learning involvement, assignment preparation, and information retrieval. However, these studies also witnessed that extreme use for entertainment and social networking reduced academic activities and concentration. Research by Eduljee et al. (2026) further found that technological access, geographic location, and digital proficiency influence students' internet usage patterns.

Several researchers have also examined the adverse effects of extreme internet usage and addiction of Internet on students' academic and behavioural outcomes. Mishra et al. (2014) and Akhter (2013) found a significant negative relationship between internet addiction and students' academic performance, indicating that excessive internet use affects time management, focus, and academic productivity. Likewise, Kirschner and Karpinski (2010) identified that extreme social networking use was associated with lower grade point in academics and reduced times given to study among university students. Kumar et al. (2020) further reported that health issues appeared due to high levels of internet addiction and academic performance also lowered among college students. A study by Balasubramanian and Parayitam (2023) showed a different result of internet addiction that highlighted that lengthy exposure to networking and entertainment apps

contributed positively to internet addiction among school and college students. These findings indicate that although the internet supports educational development, unbalanced and excessive use may negatively affect academic performance and health.

The literature also highlighted the importance of institutional support, digital literacy, and ICT infrastructure in promoting effective internet use. Talawar and Naikar (2024) highlighted that awareness and access to e-resources such as Shodhganga and N-List significantly improved research productivity among research scholars. They also highlighted the challenges like inadequate ICT infrastructure and limited search skills delay effective utilization of e-resources. Similarly, Naik and Kumar (2019) found that the behavioural intention of faculty and students was influenced by usefulness and ease of internet use. Verma et al. (2025) observed that postgraduate students used the internet for academic and research activities. Although the use is high, they demanded for digital literacy and time-management interferences. Overall, the reviewed literature indicated that the use of internet has become an essential practice in higher education where students and research scholars largely depend on it for their work. The balanced use of internet, digital capabilities, ICT infrastructure, and user training are also discussed in the past literature.

3. Objectives

1. To evaluate the impact of internet use on academic performance and research productivity.
2. To identify major challenges faced while using the internet, such as connectivity, skills, and technical support.
3. To analyze health issues associated with prolonged internet use.
4. To assess the effectiveness of university internet facilities and training programs.
5. To explore required improvements and preferred support systems for better internet use.

4. Methodology

This study accepts a quantitative method using the survey of students and research scholars working in the universities of the Kalyana Karnataka region. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of closed-ended and scaled questions that covered the impact of use of the Internet, challenges faced, and institutional support system available.

A total of 4460 students are studying in 5 Universities of Kalyana Karnataka region viz, Gulbarga

University, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Raichur University, Koppal University, Bidar University. Meanwhile, a total of 194 research scholars pursuing Ph.D in two universities of this region viz., Gulbarga University and Sri Krishnadevaraya University. In order to obtain the sample from the population, the following formula by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) was used

$$s = \frac{x^2NP(1 - P)}{d^2(N - 1) + x^2P(1 - P)}$$

using this formula and where, N for students is 4460, $x^2=3.841$ for 95% confidence level, $d=0.05$, and $p=0.5$ (standard assumption), the sample size for students is

$$\frac{3.841 \times 1115 = 4282.7}{11.1475 + 0.96025 = 12.10775} = 354.$$

Similarly, same formula was used to obtain the sample size for research scholars where, N for research scholars is 194, where only two Universities are offering Ph.D. degree viz., Gulbarga University and Sri Krishnadevaraya University, $x^2=3.841$ for 95% confidence level, $d=0.05$, and $p=0.5$ (standard assumption), and the sample size for research scholars is

$$\frac{3.841 \times 48.5 = 186.29}{0.4825 + 0.96025 = 1.44275} = 129.$$

Hence, a total of 483 respondents comprising of 354 students and 129 research scholars were included in the study.

The description statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. Frequencies, percentages, and mean values were used wherever necessary to present the data in meaningful format. The findings are presented in tabular format to simplify the data analysis and interpretation.

5. Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table 1: Gender-wise Distribution of Respondents

Gender	Students (N=354)		Research Scholars (N=129)	
	Number	%	Number	%
Male	208	58.76	68	52.71
Female	146	41.24	61	47.29
Total	354	100.00	129	100.00

Table 1 shows that male respondents form the higher percentage among students and research scholars. Among 354 students, males account for 58.76% and females for 41.24%. Similarly, among 129 research scholars, males represent 52.71%, which is slightly higher than females at 47.29%.

Table 2: Frequency of Internet Use for Academic Purposes by Students

Frequency	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Daily	280	79.10	97	75.19
Weekly	49	13.84	26	20.16
Monthly	25	7.06	6	4.65
Total	354	100.00	129	100.00

Table 2 indicates that most students use the internet daily (79.10%) followed by weekly (13.84%) and only 7.06% who use it monthly. The highest percentage, 75.19% of research scholars use the internet daily followed by 20.16% who use it weekly, while only 4.65% use it monthly. This indicates that most students and research scholars rely greatly on the internet for their academic and research work.

Table 3: Reliability of Internet Connection

Platform	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Very reliable	210	59.32	69	53.49
Reliable	54	15.25	27	20.93
Neutral	50	14.12	18	13.95
Unreliable	36	10.17	15	11.63
Very unreliable	4	1.13	0	0.00

Table 3 shows that most respondents consider their internet connection to be very reliable. Among students, the highest percentage is 59.32% for very reliable, followed by 15.25% who say it is reliable, 14.12% who feel it is neutral, and 10.17% who consider it unreliable. Among research scholars, the highest percentage is also for very reliable at 53.49%, followed by 20.93% who say reliable, 13.95% neutral, and 11.63% unreliable. When compared, students have a slightly higher perception of very reliable connections, while research scholars report a bit more in the reliable category. The percentage of unreliable responses is somewhat similar in both groups.

Table 4: Internet Use for Research Publications

Frequency	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Always	38	10.73	105	81.40
Often	48	13.56	21	16.28
Sometimes	84	23.73	3	2.33
Rarely	112	31.64	0	0.00
Never	72	20.34	0	0.00

Table 4 shows a clear difference between students and research scholars in using the internet for research publications. Among students, the highest percentage is 31.64% who rarely use the internet for this purpose. This is followed by 23.73% who sometimes use it, 20.34% who never use it, 13.56% who often use it, and only 10.73% who always use it. This indicates that students are not very actively involved in research publication work. In contrast, among research scholars, the highest percentage is 81.40% who always use the internet for research publications. This is followed by 16.28% who often use it, 2.33% who sometimes use it, and none who rarely or never use it.

Table 5: Activity Consuming Most Time

Activity	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Academic	320	90.40	0	0.00
Research	0	0.00	129	100.00
Social media	26	7.34	0	0.00
Entertainment	8	2.26	0	0.00

Table 5 shows a clear difference in how students and research scholars spend most of their time online. Among students, the highest percentage is 90.40% for academic activities, indicating that most of their time is devoted to studies. This is followed by 7.34% who spend time on social media and 2.26% on entertainment, while none reported spending most of their time on research. In contrast, among research scholars, the highest and complete percentage (100%) is for research activities, and none of them reported academic, social media, or entertainment as their main time-consuming activity.

Table 6: Impact of Internet on Academic and Research Work

Impact	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Significantly improved	280	79.10	38	29.46
Improved	38	10.73	91	70.54
No change	29	8.19	-	-
Decreased	7	1.98	-	-

Table 6 indicates that the internet has a positive impact on both students and research scholars, but in slightly different ways. Among students, the highest percentage is 79.10% who feel that the internet has significantly improved their academic work. This is followed by 10.73% who feel it has improved, 8.19% who see no change, and only 1.98% who feel it has decreased their performance.

Among research scholars, the highest percentage is 70.54% who feel that the internet has improved their work, followed by 29.46% who feel it has significantly improved. There are no responses for 'no change' or 'decreased'. When compared, students show a stronger response in the "significantly improved" category, while research scholars mostly feel it has improved steadily.

Table 7: Impact on Academic Performance

Option	Response	% (N=483)
Highly positive	268	75.71
Positive	188	53.11
Neutral	20	5.65
Negative	7	1.98

Table 7 shows that the internet has a highly positive effect on academic performance overall. The highest percentage is 75.71% who feel the impact is highly positive. This is followed by 53.11% who consider it positive, while only 5.65% feel neutral and a very small percentage of 1.98% feel it is negative. This indicates that most respondents experience clear benefits from using the internet in their academic activities. The very low percentage of negative responses suggests that problems or disadvantages are minimal. In conclusion, the internet plays an important and positive role in improving academic performance for the majority of respondents.

Table 8: Problems Faced

Problems	Most frequently	Frequently	Can't Say	Less frequently	Very less frequently	Mean
Poor connectivity	102 21.12	164 33.95	121 25.05	79 16.36	17 3.52	3.53
Low speed	125 25.88	148 30.64	111 22.98	98 20.29	1 0.21	3.62
Power cuts	20 4.14	135 27.95	120 24.84	170 35.20	38 7.87	2.85
Lack of skills	150 31.06	276 57.14	12 2.48	45 9.32	0 0.00	4.10
Security issues	13 2.69	145 30.02	158 32.71	126 26.09	41 8.49	2.92
Technical support	150 31.06	270 55.90	11 2.28	52 10.77	0 0.00	4.07

Table 8 presents the major problems faced by respondents while using the internet. The most serious issue is lack of skills, where the highest responses fall under “frequently” (57.14%) followed by “most frequently” (31.06%), showing that a large number of respondents strongly experience this problem. Only a small percentage reported it as “less frequently” (9.32%) and none as “very less frequently” (0.00%), resulting in the highest mean value (Mean=4.10). This is followed by technical support, where again the highest responses are “frequently” (55.90%) and “most frequently” (31.06%), with very few in “less frequently” (10.77%) and none in “very less frequently” (0.00%), giving a high mean (Mean=4.07).

The next major issue is low speed, where the highest responses are “frequently” (30.64%) and “most frequently” (25.88%), followed by “can’t say” (22.98%) and “less frequently” (20.29%), while very few reported “very less frequently” (0.21%), resulting in a moderate mean (Mean=3.62). Similarly, poor connectivity shows higher responses in “frequently” (33.95%) and “can’t say” (25.05%), followed by “most frequently” (21.12%) and “less frequently” (16.36%), with fewer in “very less frequently” (3.52%), giving a mean value (Mean=3.53).

Security issues show mixed opinions, with the highest responses in “can’t say” (32.71%) and “frequently” (30.02%), followed by “less frequently” (26.09%), while fewer respondents reported “very less frequently” (8.49%) and “most frequently” (2.69%), resulting in a lower mean (Mean=2.92).

Power cuts appear to be the least serious problem, where the highest responses are in “less frequently” (35.20%) and “frequently” (27.95%), followed by “can’t say” (24.84%), with fewer in “very less frequently” (7.87%) and very few in “most frequently” (4.14%), giving the lowest mean (Mean=2.85).

Table 9: Problems Faced by categories of respondents

Problems	Mean Value	
	Students	Research scholars
Poor connectivity	3.52	3.56
Low speed	3.66	3.51
Power cuts	2.86	2.83
Lack of skills	4.09	4.12
Security issues	2.93	2.91
Technical support	4.08	4.05

Table 9 compares the problems faced by students and research scholars using mean values. The highest problem for students is lack of skills (Mean=4.09), followed closely by technical support (Mean=4.08), showing that both are major concerns. For research scholars also, lack of skills (Mean=4.12) is the highest, followed by technical support (Mean=4.05), indicating a similar pattern. Low speed shows a slightly higher concern among students (Mean=3.66) compared to research scholars (Mean=3.51). Poor connectivity is almost similar for both groups, with students (Mean=3.52) and research scholars (Mean=3.56). Security issues are also nearly equal, with students (Mean=2.93) and research scholars

(Mean=2.91). Power cuts show the lowest concern for both groups, with students (Mean=2.86) and research scholars (Mean=2.83).

Table 10: Internet Addiction Level

Addiction level	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
To a very large extent	25	7.06	2	1.55
To a large extent	67	18.93	26	20.16
Can't say	42	11.86	16	12.40
To small extent	163	46.05	45	34.88
To a very small extent	57	16.10	40	31.01

Table 10 shows that most respondents fall in the lower levels of internet addiction. Among students, the highest percentage is in “to small extent” (46.05%), followed by “to a large extent” (18.93%), and “to a very small extent” (16.10%). A smaller group selected “can’t say” (11.86%), while only 7.06% reported “to a very large extent.” This indicates that most students do not feel highly addicted to the internet. Among research scholars, the highest percentage is also in “to small extent” (34.88%), followed by “to a very small extent” (31.01%), showing even lower levels of addiction. Then, 20.16% reported “to a large extent,” 12.40% said “can’t say,” and only 1.55% reported “to a very large extent.”

Table 11: University Internet Facilities

Condition of Internet	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Excellent	114	32.20	41	31.78
Good	125	35.31	39	30.23
Average	100	28.25	39	30.23
Poor	15	4.24	10	7.75

Table 11 shows how respondents rate the condition of internet facilities provided by the university. Among students, the highest percentage is “good” (35.31%), followed by “excellent” (32.20%), and then “average” (28.25%). Only a small percentage rated it as “poor” (4.24%). This indicates that most students are generally satisfied with the internet facilities, with very few expressing dissatisfaction. Among research scholars, the highest percentage is “excellent” (31.78%), followed by “good” (30.23%) and “average” (30.23%), showing a more balanced opinion across these categories. A slightly higher

percentage compared to students rated it as “poor” (7.75%).

Table 12: Benefit of Training Programs on Internet use

Benefit	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Very beneficial	194	54.80	65	50.39
Beneficial	111	31.36	46	35.66
Not beneficial	49	13.84	18	13.95

Table 12 shows how respondents perceive the benefits of training programs on use of Internet. Among students, the highest percentage is “very beneficial” (54.80%), followed by “beneficial” (31.36%), while a smaller percentage reported “not beneficial” (13.84%). This indicates that most students find the training programs helpful while using the Internet. Among research scholars, the highest percentage is also “very beneficial” (50.39%), followed by “beneficial” (35.66%), and a smaller percentage reported “not beneficial” (13.95%) in the use of Internet. When compared, both groups show similar patterns, with a majority finding the training useful. Students have a slightly higher percentage in “very beneficial,” while research scholars show slightly higher responses in the “beneficial” category. The percentage of negative responses is almost the same in both groups.

Table 13: Technological Issues

Technological issues	SA	A	CS	D	SD	Mean
University has technologically advanced infrastructure	153 (31.68)	66 (13.66)	100 (20.70)	149 (30.85)	15 (3.11)	3.40
Internet access be increased	131 (27.12)	83 (17.18)	128 (26.50)	137 (28.36)	4 (0.83)	3.41
Recommend policy changes	131 (27.12)	90 (18.63)	125 (25.88)	137 (28.36)	0 (0.00)	3.45
Digital resources are sufficient	131 (27.12)	79 (16.36)	121 (25.05)	144 (29.81)	8 (1.66)	3.37
Wi-Fi facility need to be improved	61 (12.63)	119 (24.64)	133 (27.54)	134 (27.74)	36 (7.45)	3.07

Table 13 presents respondents’ opinions on technological aspects using agreement levels. For the statement “University has technologically advanced infrastructure,” the highest responses are in “strongly agree” (31.68%) and “disagree” (30.85%), followed by “can’t say” (20.70%), “agree” (13.66%), and fewer in “strongly disagree” (3.11%), resulting in a moderate mean (Mean=3.40). For “Internet access be increased,” the highest responses are in “disagree” (28.36%) and “can’t say” (26.50%), followed by “strongly agree” (27.12%) and “agree” (17.18%), with very few in “strongly disagree” (0.83%), giving a mean (Mean=3.41).

For “Recommend policy changes,” the highest responses are in “disagree” (28.36%) and “can’t say” (25.88%), followed by “strongly agree” (27.12%) and “agree” (18.63%), with none in “strongly disagree” (0.00%), resulting in a mean (Mean=3.45). For “Digital resources are sufficient,” the highest responses are in “disagree” (29.81%) and “strongly agree” (27.12%), followed by “can’t say” (25.05%) and “agree” (16.36%), with fewer in “strongly disagree” (1.66%), giving a mean (Mean=3.37).

For “Wi-Fi facility need to be improved,” the highest responses are in “disagree” (27.74%) and “can’t say” (27.54%), followed by “agree” (24.64%) and “strongly agree” (12.63%), with some in “strongly disagree” (7.45%), resulting in the lowest mean among the statements (Mean=3.07). When compared across all statements, the mean values are close, indicating moderate opinions without strong agreement or disagreement. However, slightly higher means for policy changes and internet access suggest a need for improvement.

Table 14: Overall Satisfaction about Internet facility

Level of satisfaction	Students		Research Scholars	
	Number	%	Number	%
Very High	16	4.52	8	6.20
High	82	23.16	36	27.91
Moderate	132	37.29	42	32.56
Low	109	30.79	43	33.33
Very Low	15	4.24	0	0.00

Table 14 shows the overall satisfaction levels of students and research scholars about internet facility available. Among students, the highest percentage is in the moderate category (37.29%), followed by low satisfaction (30.79%), and then high satisfaction (23.16%). Smaller percentages are seen in very high

(4.52%) and very low (4.24%) categories. This indicates that most students feel moderately satisfied, but a considerable number also report low satisfaction. Among research scholars, the highest percentage is also moderate (32.56%), followed closely by low satisfaction (33.33%), and then high satisfaction (27.91%). A smaller percentage reported very high satisfaction (6.20%), and none reported very low satisfaction (0.00%).

6. Discussion and Conclusion

The study found that most respondents are satisfied with their internet connection, though a small percentage of them faces issues. The respondents stated that the internet reliability is generally good, but there is still options for improvement. It is found that research scholars show a very strong and regular use of the internet for publications, while students used for academic purposes. This clearly reflects the different academic roles of the two groups. The students focus mainly on academic learning, while research scholars are fully dedicated to research work which indicates that students spend most of their time on academic tasks, whereas research scholars spend it entirely on research activities. Meanwhile, it is clear that both groups benefit from the internet, though their level of insights varies slightly. The internet has a strong positive impact on academic and research work for both groups.

The students and research scholars have encountered all problems; the lack of skills and technical support stand out as the most serious challenges, while power cuts and security issues are relatively less severe for both. The main difficulties faced by respondents are related to skill gaps and lack of proper technical support, which need more attention for effective internet use. Further, research scholars have shown higher expectations about university internet facilities. Both students and research scholars show mixed opinions on technological issues, with reasonable agreement indicating that while Internet facilities exist, there is still options for improvement in ICT infrastructure and Internet services. The Universities need to focus more on these issues to provide continuous technical support and develop state of the art ICT infrastructure. To overcome the skill gap issues, the libraries of Universities shall conduct frequent orientation programs that demonstrate the information search skills and their ethical usage among students and research scholars.

Both students and research scholars show low levels of addiction overall, but students have highly addicted to Internet than research scholars. This

suggests that research scholars may have more controlled internet usage, which needs to be followed by the student community for safe browsing. The study witnessed overall satisfaction level is moderate for both groups on the internet facility available in the Universities, with some scope for improvement, especially demanded by students.

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